

**COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LEXEMES WITH NEGATIVE
ELEMENTS OF THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8041795>

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to comparative study of lexemes with negative elements by means of componential and syntaxeme analyses based on junctional and componential models. In the process of the investigation isomorphism and allomorphy of revealed syntaxemes with negative elements have been determined in the structure of sentences in the English and Uzbek languages.

Key words: *negativity, componential model, junctional model, nuclear predicated, un-nuclear dependent, negative affixes, prefixes, suffixes, coordinative components.*

In modern English and Uzbek, negative affixes play a crucial role in expressing negativity. In both languages, negative affixes are classified into prefixes and suffixes. And negative affixes are considered to be the most productive way to make negative elements by attaching to nouns, adjectives and verbs.

Negative suffixes *-less* (in English) and *-siz* (in Uzbek) are typically attached to nouns forming adjectives:

lifeless- jonsiz, groundless- asossiz, dalilsiz, weightless – ahamiyatsiz, stainless – dog’siz.

It must be noted that adjective suffix *-siz* (forming adjectives) in the Uzbek language can be expressed by a number of negative prefixes (forming adjectives) in the English language:

- un+A=unlucky-baxtsiz
- im+A=imponderable-ahamiyatsiz
- siz----- ill+A= ill-favoured-ko’rksiz, ko’rimsiz
- in+A=insignificant-ma’nosiz, ahamiyatsiz
- dis+A=disrespectful-hurmatsiz, yuzsiz
- non+A=noncellular-hujayrasiz
- ir+A=irrelevant-o’rinsiz

So, suffix *-siz* is commonly used in the formation of adjectives in the Uzbek language. But for words derived from Persian, the suffix *-siz* is sometimes replaced by the prefix *be-*, and it can be expressed in English using the following prefixes:

- im+A=impatient-betoqat-sabrsiz
- dis+A=disrespectful-beadab, surbet
- be-----un+A=unwise-befahm, fahmsiz
- in+A=inaudible-beshovqin, sharpasiz
- ir+A=irresponsible-beixtiyor, ongsiz

-----un+A=unmersiful-berahm, rahmsiz

Furthermore, the prefix *no-* (in English) forms an adjective from nouns and words denoting properties of smth.or smb. When it is added to nouns, it denotes an absence of possession of that object, and when it is added to words denoting properties, it creates adjectives that contradict the primary meaning. It can be used in the English language by the following prefixes:

-----un+A=unworthy-nomunosib

-----im+A=imprudent-noma'qul

-----ab+S = abnormality-nomuntazamlik

no-----ir+A=irregular-noto'g'ri

-----in+A=ingratitude noshukur

-----il+A =illegal=nolegal

-----dis+A=dissatisfied-norozi

-----non+S = nonagreement-norozilik

From the previous examples, it is understood that suffixes and prefixes denoting negation in the Uzbek language are translated into English by using various prefixes besides the suffix *-less*. Similarly, negative prefixes in the English language can be found in various variants while translating into Uzbek.

The negative prefix *un-* can be represented in the Uzbek language as follows:

-----siz -N=unconscientiousness-vidonsizlik

un-----ma +gan- A=undesirable-istalmagan

-----ma+s- A=unforgettable-unutilmas

-----siz - A=unlucky-baxtsiz

-----no -A=undeserved-nohaq

English prefixes such as *dis-*, *in-*, *ir-*, *im-*, *pop-*, *mis-*, *il-* and *un-* can be translated in a variety of ways into the Uzbek language.

The position of syntactic units with negative elements in the structure of sentence, their connections with other elements of the sentence, syntactic relations, differentiative syntactic signs, identifying the process of expressing complete or partial negation in sentences and determining their semantic field at the syntactic level is the primary goal and task, and we have limited to observe units with negative affixes in the sentences. (1.148.)

Based on the preceding examples, it can be stated that different negative affixes are used in the process of translation English negative affixes into Uzbek, the same issue can be met in the Uzbek language too. This is reflected in the sentences as well:

1. *Iago. You charge me most unjustly. (Shakespeare)*

Yago.Siz meni juda nohaq aldayotibsiz. (Shekspir)

Sometimes English sentences with negative components are translated with the help of antonym words in the Uzbek language:

2) *Pap unlocked the door (M.Twain)*

Eshikni ochib berdi (M.Tven)

3) *Gratiano. 'Tis some mischance, the cry is very direful (Shakespeare)*

Grasiana. Bu yerda bir fojia bor! Birov ingraydi. (Shekspir)

Syntactic units with negative affixes can appear in the following syntactic positions in the structure of the sentence in the English language:

1. In the position of the component of nuclear predicative₁(NP₁):

An angry surge of disappointment made her quicken her steps. (D. Carter)

2.1 In the position of the component of nuclear predicative₂(NP₂):

My Board is intolerable. (D. Carter)

He unlocked the door (D. Carter)

2.2. In the position of the component of coordinative nuclear predicative₂(HNP₂):

*Gemma unlocked a drawer and took out several sheets
paper (E. I. Voinich)*

3. In the position of the component of un-nuclear predicative₂ (NP₂): —

That passed unnoticed. (D. Carter)

The thing makes one feel unhappy. (E.L.Voinich)

4.1. In the position of the component of un-nuclear dependent (ND): —

The early September sun edged down behind the treeless ridge. (E. L. Voinich)

*The brassy whistle was curiously mellowed by countless reflections on the
boulders of Deep Rock.(D.Carter)*

4.2. In the position of the component of coordinative un-nuclear dependent (HND): —

He cared for the broken and dishonored idols. (E.L.Voinich)

Syntactic units with negative affixes can appear in the following syntactic positions in the structure of sentences in the Uzbek language:

1. In the position of the component of nuclear predicative₁ (NP₁):

Nobakorlar yomon rejalar bilan mashg'uldir. (O.Yoqubov)

Beg'ubor bolalik. (O.Yoqubov)

2. In the position of the component of nuclear predicative₂ (NP₂):

Butun mamlakat notinch(O.Yoqubov)

Jangchila r bilan ham nopisand (B.Raxmon)

2.1. In the position of the component of un-nuclear predicative₂ (NP₂):

Sen Pirmatovni noloyiq hisoblaysan. (B.Raxmon)

2.2. In the position of the component of coordinative nuclear predicative₂ (HNP₂):

Bu odam hozir allaqanday besabr va betoqat edi. (O.Yoqubov)

3. In the position of the component of un-nuclear dependent (ND): —

Men gunohsiz o'lmoqdaman. (Shekspir)

Noobod yalangliklar orqada qolib ketdi. (B.Raxmon)

3.1. In the position of the component of coordinative un-nuclear dependent (HND): —

Beqiyos, behudud bog'ni Firuza egallagan. (O.Yoqubov)

Elements with negative affixes in both languages have got isomorphic features according to their positions in sentences. Syntactic units with negative affixes in the position of nuclear predicative₁ are primarily represented by cognate nouns and they are connected by means of nuclear predicative connection with the nuclear predicative₂. (2.16.)

In the English language, the component of nuclear predictive₂ is formed in the following ways:

1. Vf (finite form of the verb):

Rupert unfastened the heavy fur coat. (E.L.Voinich)

2. to be+ Ven:

The door is unlocked, and there is no moon. (E.L.Voinich)

3. to be+ A;

The sky was cloudless. (E.L.Voinich)

4. to be+S:

The thing is so unbusiness like. (E.L.Voinich)

It is known that syntactic analysis of the structure of the sentence in traditional grammar means to determine the primary and secondary parts of the sentence, but such kind of syntactic analysis is limited by designing primary and secondary parts of the sentence and it is based only on formal side of the sentence. "Such kind of defects in the syntactic analysis of the sentence are not based on any concrete linguistic methods". (4.p.50.)

A.M.Mukhin created new linguistic methods of analysis of the sentence as componential and syntaxeme analyses.

The surface structure of the sentence is identified with the help of componential analysis. The main task of componential analysis is to define syntactic connections between(among) syntactic units in the structure of the sentence. (3.41.) And syntaxeme analysis (deep structure of the sentence) presents an opportunity to reveal differential syntactic-semantic signs of defined components and their variants in the structure of the sentence.

Professor A.M.Mukhin confirmed that there are three types of categorial differential syntactic-semantic signs in syntaxeme analysis: processuality, substantiality and qualificativity .

According to A.M.Mukhin's consideration "Prosessuality is a syntactic unit which expresses either an action or a state; Substantiality can be expressed by means of pronoun, noun denoting a person, an objectivity; Qualificativity expresses the signs of an object or person, their quantity, state and manner of the action"(5.p.155.)

Componential and juncial models can be widely used in carrying out componential and syntaxeme analyses.

1) We tried to use such kind of models in the process of componential analysis:

Non-metals form negative elements.

$$\frac{NP_1}{S} \cdot \frac{NP_2}{Vf} \cdot \frac{\tilde{N}D}{A} \cdot \frac{\tilde{N}D}{S} \quad \text{a) Componential model (c.m.)}$$

b) Junctional model (j.m.)

a) The symbol- NP_1 -*Non-metals* means the subject of the sentence (N- means nuclear, P_1 -predicated means that the subject of the sentence is defined by the predicate).

a) The symbol - NP_2 -*form* means the predicate of the sentence (P_2 -predicating that expresses the centre of the sentence).

b) The symbol - ND - *negative elements* means un-nuclear dependent component.

Syntaxeme analyses of the sentence structure is based on, first of all, to determine categorical syntactic-semantic signs of components as substantiality which means (person or object, location etc), processuality – (action or state) and qualificativity- (degree, quality, number, state, etc). (6.119.) According to those categorical syntactic- semantic signs of components we can reveal non- categorical syntactic-semantic signs of components in the structure of the sentence.

2.The next stage is a syntaxeme analysis of the sentence:

Non-metals form negative elements.

SbAgPrAc Q1fQ1tSbOb

- a) The syntactic unit *Nonmetals* express substantiality (**Sb**) and to the attitude of *form-agentivity* (**Ag**).
- b) The syntactic unit **form** is a processual and actional (**PrAc**) syntaxeme.
- c) The syntactic unit *negative* in the position of attribute expresses qualificative qualitative syntaxeme and it relates to substantial object syntaxeme - *elements* as **Q1fQ1t**.
- d) The syntactic unit *elements* expresses substantial object syntaxeme and to the attitude of *form-objectivity*-**SbOb**.

According to the results of the analyses it can be concluded that componential and syntaxeme analyses based on componential and junctional models have got a number of advantageous points:

1. Peculiarities of form and content of syntactic units of the sentence can be found out by means of componential and syntaxeme analyses.
2. The main task of componential analysis is to define syntactic connections between or among syntactic units and differentiate defined syntactic units in the structure of the sentence.
3. The most crucial case of syntaxeme analysis is that sentences having the same componential and junctional models of components can possess various categorial differential syntactic-semantic signs of syntactic units in the structure of the sentence.
4. Componential and syntaxeme analyses of the sentence can fill each other which present a great opportunity to explain the essence of form and content of syntactic units in the structure of the sentence.

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